

U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service

ECOS

ECOS /

Bermuda petrel (*Pterodroma cahow*)

[Range Information](#) | [Candidate Info](#) | [Federal Register](#) | [Recovery](#) | [Critical Habitat](#) | [SSA](#) | [Conservation Plans](#) | [Petitions](#) | [Biological Opinions](#) | [Life History](#)

Taxonomy: [View taxonomy in ITIS](#)

Listing Status: Endangered

Where Listed: WHEREVER FOUND

General Information

38 cm. Medium-sized, long-winged, brownish-grey and white gadfly petrel. Brownish-black cap extending to eye, but interrupted by pale eyebrow. Brownish nape extending towards upper breast to form partial collar. Brownish-grey mantle, upperwing and tail. Pale uppertail-coverts may form narrow whitish band. Entirely white underparts. White underwing with narrow black trailing edge, black tip, extending narrowly onto leading edge. Black bill. Pink legs, pink feet proximally, black distally.

Current Listing Status Summary

Show 10 entries

Status	Date Listed	Lead Region	Where Listed
Endangered	06-02-1970	Southeast Region (Region 4)	Wherever found Additional species information

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

< Previous 1 Next >

» Range Information

Current Range

Last Updated: 03-17-2025 - Wherever found

Zoom in! Some species' locations may be small and hard to see from a wide perspective. To narrow-in on locations, check the state and county lists (below) and then use the zoom tool.

Want the FWS's current range for all species? Click [here](#) to download a zip file containing all individual shapefiles and metadata for all species.

* For consultation needs do not use only this current range map, please use [IPaC](#).

Current range maps are only shown within the jurisdictional boundaries of the United States of America. The species may also occur outside this region.

- **Wherever found**

Listing status: Endangered

- **States/US Territories** in which this population is known to or is believed to occur: Florida, Massachusetts, North Carolina, South Carolina, Virginia
- **US Counties** in which this population is known to or is believed to occur: [View All](#)
- **USFWS Refuges** in which this population is known to occur:
- **Countries** in which this population is known to occur: Bermuda, United States

» Candidate Information

No Candidate information available for this species.

No Candidate Assessments available for this species.

No Candidate Notice of Review Documents currently available for this species.

No Uplisting Documents currently available for this species.

» Federal Register Documents
Federal Register Documents

Show entries

Date	Citation Page	Title	Supporting Documents
05/11/2023	88 FR 30324 30328	Initiation of 5-Year Status Reviews for 67 Southeastern Species	
05/07/2018	83 FR 20092 20095	5-Year Status Reviews for 35 Southeastern Species	
09/21/2007	72 FR 54057 54059	5-Year Review of 16 Southeastern Species	
06/02/1970	35 FR 8491 8498	Part 17 - Conservation of Endangered Species and Other Fish or Wildlife (First List of Endangered Foreign Fish and Wildlife as Appendix A)	
04/14/1970	35 FR 6069	Notice of Proposed Rulemaking (Endangered Species Conservation); 35 FR 6069	

Showing 1 to 5 of 5 entries

< Previous 1 Next >

» Species Status Assessments (SSAs)
Species Status Assessments (SSAs)

No Species Status Assessments (SSA's) are currently available for this species.

Special Rule Publications

No Special Rule Publications currently available for this species.

» Recovery

- [Species with Recovery Documents Data Explorer](#)
- Recovery Priority Number: 2

No Current Recovery Plans available for this species.

Other Recovery Documents

Note: This report includes actual Five Year Review completions and notices as well as records that act as Five Year Review completions and notices.

Show entries

Date	Citation Page	Title	Document Type
05/11/2023	88 FR 30324 30328	Initiation of 5-Year Status Reviews for 67 Southeastern Species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Five Year Review Notice, Information Solicitation
05/07/2018	83 FR 20092 20095	5-Year Status Reviews for 35 Southeastern Species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Five Year Review Notice, Information Solicitation
09/21/2007	72 FR 54057 54059	5-Year Review of 16 Southeastern Species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Five Year Review Notice, Information Solicitation

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries

< Previous	1	Next >
------------	---	--------

Five Year Reviews

Note: This report includes actual Five Year Review completions as well as records that act as Five Year Review completions.

Show entries

Date	Title
11/25/2024	Bermuda Petrel (<i>Pterodroma cahow</i>) 5-Year Status Review 2024
08/20/2019	Bermuda petrel(<i>Pterodroma cahow</i>) 5-Year Review
10/30/2013	Bermuda petrel(<i>Pterodroma cahow</i>) 5-Year Review

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries

< Previous	1	Next >
------------	---	--------

No Delisting Documents currently available for this species.

» Critical Habitat

No Critical Habitat Documents currently available for this species.

» Conservation Plans

No Conservation Plans currently available for this species.

» Petitions

No Petitions currently available for this species.

» Biological Opinions

To see all FWS Issued Biological Opinions please visit the [BO Report](#).

» Life History

No Life History information has been entered into this system for this species.

» Other Resources

[NatureServe Explorer Species Reports](#)-- NatureServe Explorer is a source for authoritative conservation information on more than 50,000 plants, animals and ecological communities of the U.S and Canada. NatureServe Explorer provides in-depth information on rare and endangered species, but includes common plants and animals too. NatureServe Explorer is a product of NatureServe in collaboration with the Natural Heritage Network.

[ITIS Reports](#)-- ITIS (the Integrated Taxonomic Information System) is a source for authoritative taxonomic information on plants, animals, fungi, and microbes of North America and the world.

[FWS Digital Media Library](#).-- The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service's National Digital Library is a searchable collection of selected images, historical artifacts, audio clips, publications, and video." +